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Aqp10 activation as a model for therapeutic strategies that incorporate re-activation measures.

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Citations

1. Gotfryd, K., Mósca, A.F., Missel, J.W., Truelsen, S.F., Wang, K., Spulber, M., Krabbe, S., Hélix-Nielsen, C., Laforenza, U., Soveral, G. and Pedersen, P.A., 2018. Human adipose glycerol flux is regulated by a pH gate in AQP10. Nature communications, 9(1), p.4749.